
EDUCATIONAL AND SOCIAL ISSUES IN THE WORK OF EVELYN WAUGH AND JULIAN MITCHELL

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Abstract: This article based on Evelyn Waugh’s works and Julian Mitchell’s works. It has shown similar issues of the educational systems, social orders, human’s value in the same society. Difference between works is about a half century.

Keywords: satire, Enlightenment period, irony, satirical tone, interview, educational system.

History depicts full of the transformations of the human nature and other developments of social life, cultural heritages, value of the religions in the society. There are several issues or problems still remain nowadays also. The writers have shown us them in their works, insuring society or people and the governments for a change in better ways. Most writers or novelists used to write in a satirical tone to show how bitter the situations are. “**Satire**, artistic form, chiefly literary and dramatic, in which human or individual vices, follies, abuses, or shortcomings are held up to censure by means of ridicule, derision, burlesque, irony, parody, caricature, or other methods, sometimes with an intent to inspire social reform.”¹ In some works, the usage of the stylistic devices is visible, but in other works the readers only could feel the satirical tones from the contexts. In fact, the usage of the satire is for reconstructing social values or showing the behavior of the society for themselves or others as a mirror.

If we look at the development of satire in the works of English satirists such as Alexander Pope from Enlightenment period, and with his famous discursive poetry “The rape of the Lock”, an English critic, Samuel Johnson works “Age of Reason”, an English writer of the satirical novels, Evelyn Waugh’s “Decline and Fall” and “A Handful of Dust”, and an English author, Malcolm Bradbury’s “White Father”, “The History Man” and John Mitchell’s “Another country” and this list is still going on. In Russian literature, we can define satirists such as Anton Checkov and his works “Человек в футляре”, “Смерть Чиновника” and Alexandr Kuprin, a novelist, “The Garnet Bracelet” (“Гранатовый браслет”) (1911) and an Uzbek playwright and a translator, Abdulla Kahhar.

An English satirical novelist, Evelyn Waugh, was famous with his works “Decline and Fall” and “Handful of the Dust”. “Decline and Fall”(1928) is about the life of the man who was named Paul Pennyfeather. He was accepted for work

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/art/courtesy-literature>

because of the director of the school. The director of the school thought he would be son-in-law for him in the future, planning his daughter and Paul would get married one day. When it comes to school stuff, they thought different school subjects unrelated to their educations. Describing them it was a normal case. The author with his life shows the problems of the society in England, on education system, social norms, family relationship or family values, the role of the social status, human orientations, sense of injustice among people in that society. An occasional novelist, Julian Mitchell’s well known play “Another Country” (1981) illustrates the same social problems in education system, social norms of elite boarding schools, people’s orientations, politics and social orders in there. In “Another Country”, the main character is Guy Bennett, a spy in the play. In the interview with Julian Mitchell, he said : “I also thought about this whole business of these schools, the training you get being considered a training for life. Well, If you find during the course of that, that you are not acceptable, and you are ambitious and were hoping for the high prizes of life, it might be a very good cause to make you turn, to make you feel bitter and want revenge.”² That’s Julian Mitchell’s thought for his own work. He was worried about the things which happen in schools. Showing issues of the educational places and conveying a message for the whole parents who are going to send or believe in their children’s future to the school administrations. The parents sent their children along a thought in the work. Then, these children would become the leaders of the British society. It was the reason

When it comes for the names of the work Evelyn Waugh’s “Decline and Fall” is the depiction of Edward Gibbon's “Decline and Fall of the Roman Empire” and the falling of the society of that country. Waugh through his whole novel showed the situations, politics, love affairs, human values, social orders and social norms of his country. On the other hand, Julian Mitchell’s “Another Country” named that due to the poem “I Vow To Thee, My Country” by Cecil Spring Rice. “It was sung at my prep school at the Remembrance Day service and it was always a very emotional occasion, says Mitchell in his interview. The line “and there’s another country...” is of course referring to heaven.³ It was what the author want to see his country.

Popularity and familiarity of the issues led to the revolution on the educational systems in England. For Evelyn Waugh and Julian Mitchell their works brought criticism from their friends, family members, but they showed the weakness of the society and social norms and values in government and educational systems. The authors wrote their works with irony, sometimes with literal way, sometimes with a bitter way, but anyway they impact with their messages on the society and

² McCaul, Barmet. "Julian Mitchell on 'Another Country'." *OutRage*, no. 22, Mar. 1985, pp. 30+. Archives of Sexuality and Gender.

³ <https://www.spectator.co.uk/article/julian-mitchell-on-another-country-i-based-it-on-my-fury-and-anger-and-i-wrote-it-fast-and-it-flowed/>

governments. Both authors showed their patriotic feelings, normal social values and social orders of the young people and teenagers through lives of the heroes of the works.

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